

INVESTIGATION OF THE STRUCTURE OF THERMOPLASTIC POLYESTER-POLYOL BY THE TURBIDIMETRIC METHOD

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Abstract: This study presents the turbidimetric analysis of a polyester-polyol synthesized on the basis of adipic acid and ethylene glycol. According to the research results, the addition of a precipitant sharply increases the optical density of the solution. This indicates the complete precipitation of oligomers from the solution and makes it possible to characterize their distribution by molecular weight.

Keywords: Polyester-polyol, turbidimetric analysis, optical density, solubility, precipitant.

Poliefir-poliollar kimyo sanoatida keng qo'llaniladigan muhim oligomerik birikmalar bo'lib, ular turli xil polimer materiallar ishlab chiqarishda asosiy xom ashyo hisoblanadi. Ularning eritmadan cho'kish jarayonini o'rganish polimerlarning molekulyar xususiyatlari, tuzilishi va barqarorligini tushunishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu ishda adipin kislotasi va etilenglikol asosida sintez qilingan (ADEG) poliefir-poliol ning dimetilformamid (DMF) eritmasida turbidimetrik titrlash usuli yordamida o'rganilgan natijalar bayon qilinadi.

Dastavval, antratsen va konsentrlangan sulfat kislotaning o'zaro mexanik aralashmalari mavjud erituvchilarda erish jarayonlari ko'rib chiqildi (1-jadval).

Nº	Solvent name	Mechanical mixture	Polyester-polyol
1	Distilled water	Insoluble	Insoluble
2	Ethanol	Insoluble	Insoluble, solution turbid
3	Acetone	Slightly soluble, turbid	Soluble, solution turbid
4	Benzene	Insoluble	Soluble, solution transparent

5	Dimethylformamide	Soluble, transparent	Soluble, transparent
6	Cyclohexanone	Partially soluble	Soluble, solution turbid
7	Isobutanol	Insoluble	Insoluble

The solubility characteristics of the mechanical mixture of adipic acid and ethylene glycol, as well as of the polyester-polyol synthesized on their basis, are presented in the table. The obtained results show that the mechanical mixture is insoluble or only partially soluble in many solvents, since the components exist without chemical bonding. In contrast, after the polyester-polyol is synthesized, its molecular structure is formed through stable chemical bonds, and as a result, it dissolves well in polar organic solvents.

As seen from the table, water and higher alcohols (ethanol, isobutanol) are unsuitable for both systems: the mechanical mixture is insoluble in these media, while the polyester-polyol gives a turbid solution. Dimethylformamide (DMF) turned out to be the best solvent. Both the mechanical mixture and the polyester-polyol dissolve completely in DMF, producing a transparent solution. In addition, benzene is a good solvent for the polyester-polyol, forming a clear solution, but it is not effective for the mechanical mixture. In cyclohexanone, the polyester-polyol dissolves, but the solution appears turbid.

As a precipitant, distilled water is most suitable for the mechanical mixture, as it produces a precipitate in a short time. For the polyester-polyol system, the most effective precipitants are water and ethanol, which ensure the precipitation of the polymer from transparent solutions in DMF or benzene.

Thus, based on the conducted experiments, dimethylformamide was determined to be the most suitable solvent for both systems. As a precipitant, water is recommended for the mechanical mixture, while water or ethanol is suitable for the polyester-polyol.

Now, we proceed with our research by directly carrying out turbidimetric titration of each sample. In this case, the reaction product synthesized from adipic acid and ethylene glycol at a 1:1.1 mol/mol ratio, as well as the mechanical mixtures of the main components prepared in the same ratio, were subjected to turbidimetric titration. The corresponding titration curves were obtained (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dependence of the solution's optical density on the amount of precipitant.

Here: 1) Mechanical mixture at a 1:1.1 mol/mol ratio: solvent – dimethylformamide; precipitant – distilled water. 2) synthesized at a 1:1.1 mol/mol ratio: solvent – dimethylformamide; precipitant – ethanol.

From the first curve of this graph, it can be seen that when ethanol is gradually added (up to 1.5 ml) to a 1% solution of the hydroxyl-containing polyester-polyol in dimethylformamide, the optical density of the system (characterizing the turbidity of the solution) gradually increases. Subsequently, the addition of a small amount of precipitant causes a sharp rise in optical density. This behavior continues until about 3.6 ml of precipitant is added. Specifically, when 1.5 ml of precipitant is introduced, the optical density increases to 0.125 D, while at 3.6 ml it reaches 1.345 D. Beyond this point, further addition of precipitant does not change the optical density, indicating that the precipitation of oligomers from the solution is complete. The nature of the turbidimetric titration curve can reasonably be explained by the sequential precipitation of molecules of identical structure but differing molecular weights.

The second curve in the graph represents the turbidimetric titration of the mechanical mixture of adipic acid (AD) and ethylene glycol (EG) at a 1:1 mol/mol ratio. In this case, the addition of 0.3 ml to 1.2 ml of precipitant results in a marked increase in optical density, from 0.126 D to 0.448 D. This state partially stabilizes around 0.456–0.466 D until the addition of 2.4 ml of precipitant. Subsequent increases in precipitant volume lead to a sharp rise in optical density, which continues until 4.2 ml of precipitant is added. When 4.8 ml of precipitant is

introduced, the optical density reaches 1.134 D and remains unchanged thereafter.

A detailed analysis of this curve highlights the binary nature of the system. That is, the increase in optical density between 0.3 ml and 2.4 ml of precipitant corresponds to the precipitation of the first component, after which the second component begins to precipitate. With the addition of 4.8 ml of precipitant, the second component also fully precipitates. This sequential process is characteristic of mechanical mixtures of two different oligomers and can be described by two distinct curves.

In summary, the first curve in the figure corresponds to oligomers with a uniform chemical structure consisting of macromolecules, whereas the second curve reflects the behavior of multicomponent systems, specifically mixtures of two types of oligomers.

The turbidimetric titration results demonstrate clear differences between synthesized polyester-polyol and the mechanical mixture of adipic acid with ethylene glycol. The polyester-polyol exhibits a single, smooth precipitation curve, indicating the presence of oligomers with a uniform chemical structure and stable macromolecular bonds. In contrast, the mechanical mixture produces a two-stage titration curve, reflecting its multicomponent nature and the sequential precipitation of different oligomers. Overall, the study confirms that turbidimetric analysis is an effective method for characterizing solubility, precipitation behavior, and molecular distribution in polyester-polyol systems.

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